

The Female World of William Golding

Dr. Umesh Sharma

Associate Professor, Dept. of English, K.R. (P.G.) College, Mathura

Corresponding author- **Dr. Umesh Sharma**

Email- **Dr. Umesh Sharma**

Abstract

William Golding was versatile genius. He wrote novels, plays, short stories, poems and essays. With all these talents, he was sure to win the best of honours in the world of literature. William Golding presents a variety of women characters in his fictional world: As a novelist he has a deep penetrating insight into the life of modern men and women. The women's world in William Golding is not very large. His basic concern is to make a psychological study of man-woman relationship. In his novels we see that sometimes woman has a free fall and other times she becomes an agent in the hands of man to add to the decline of human values. Family in British society is a small unit: it is not as vast as it is in the Eastern society. There are families in William Golding but they are in most of the cases, single units, When we read William Golding's novels, we find that the central characters in novels are men. There are less women characters in his novels. But still they play an important role in the novels. He presents women in various roles. They are teachers, housewives, clerks, nurses, students, labourers and prostitutes. The female world of William Golding is very limited but significant.

Introduction

Lord of The Flies, the first great novel of William Golding, is remarkable for its absence of female characters. There is no woman in the novel, William Golding presents the early man and woman in another novel The Inheritors. There the man is concerned as much for woman as woman is concerned for man. It may be noted that there is an absolute harmony in human relationship. Woman has a central position in the social organisation. She is the mother and she is the creator. Golding has the popular myth of the mother-worship with him. It has been going on through the ages and still there are matriarchal societies in certain tribes. Golding does not present his Neanderthals as a matriarchal society but the importance of woman is quite evident. They believe that the world was created out of mother earth. "There was the great Oa. She brought forth the earth from her belly. She gave suck. The earth brought forth woman and the woman brought forth the first man out of her belly."¹ Creation itself depends on woman since there can be no man without woman. The Neanderthals society, as presented by William Golding attaches great importance to woman. She is the mother, she is the creator and the earth came out of her belly. Woman is Goddess and she is worshiped. In this world of woman two persons share a woman without jealousy and rivalry. The old man is the most vulnerable and then it is the old woman. William Golding in his novel The Pyramid proves that a great social comedy cannot be written without the central place being given to women characters. Women characters, good or bad, must be there. In this novel we are in Stillbourne, a British village where Oliver, the young son of the dispenser is in love with Imogen who is already "engaged to be married." The eighteen year lad, Oliver is a love-lorn chap. Soon there is a second girl Evie Babbacombe. Evie is a local phenomenon and she is

already moving about with Robert, the son of Dr. Evan. "She was our local phenomenon and every male for miles round was aware of her."² Besides the mother of Oliver and Evie, We have Miss Dawlish, who teaches music to Oliver. Darkness Visible a war novel begins with the havoc produced by bombardment. In William Golding women are frivolous, most of them, and most of the time. Mr. Hanrahan the owner has seven daughters and he counted them. To teach them a lesson against frivolity, Mr. Hanrahan exhibited Matty to them. Matty now keeps a journal and records all the incidents around him. Certain spirits visit him and he notes that "the spiritual life is a time of trial."³ The reader is introduced to more darkness through little girls from Sprawson's.

The darkness becomes visible when we read of Sophy and Toni, Stanhope, the twins. The mother had gone to live with a man in New Zealand and evidently woman becomes either a victim of man's mischief or herself a mischief-monger. The father's relationship with Sophy is peculiar. He is "the wooing Daddy" and girls have a free play and the father spends his time with auntie, one after the other. The mischief in the female kind is natural. William Golding studies adolescence of the two girls - Sophy and Toni. Toni runs away from her house knowing that she was "Antonia". She is now a missing person, must have got rid of her virginity, thought Sophy. She tried a couple of boys and finally it was a man in a van. Now she is happy that she has lost her virginity, it is nothing to her. Then she becomes a regular whore. His another novel 'The Paper Man' presents woman as a fallen character. It is the story of a popular novelist, Wilfred Barclay. Professor, Rick L. Tucker comes from over-seas to become the official biographer of the novelist. There are some important women characters who are partly projected in the novel.

There is Lucinda who is responsible for the beginning of the end of the writer's marriage to Elizabeth or Liz and the writer had frequent duels. Now Professor Tucker introduced Mary Lou Tucker to the novelist and now the husband and wife are after Barclay. The professor does his best to pursue Barclay to appoint him his official biographer. He has failed, so there is the woman. She is used as a bait for the novelist and professor Tucker leaves Mary Lou with Barclay in the hotel. Mary Lou is there with Barclay and she puts herself at the disposal of Barclay. Barclay has a passion for sex and dreams but Mary Lou with all her charms, fails to get the signature of Barclay authorising Tucker to write his biography. The professor did not know how to offer the woman to the client, "Pimp, client and whore, all we three needed the assistance of a professional."⁴ His another novel "The Spire" is a one man concern – Dean Joceline. The dean has a vision that he must have four hundred feet high spire in the cathedral. It will be constructed of wood, stone and metal. Women enter the plot of the story though they do not play a leading role. They have an entertainment value in the presentation of events and add to hasten the fall of man. Pangall is seen with his broom and his wife Goody is with him helping him in his task. Pangall is ridiculed by every one because he is lame and has a beautiful wife. Roger Mason is the master builder. He knows that the building of such a high spire is nothing but a folly of Joceline. His wife, Rachel, Jealously guards him. Joceline happened to see Roger Mason and Goody eyeing each other. "He saw they were in some sort of tent that shut them off from all other people and he saw how they feared the tent both of them but were helpless. Now they were talking earnestly and quietly and though Goody shook her head again and again, yet she did not go, could not go, if seemed, since the invisible tent was shut round them."⁵

The women's world of William Golding is a farcical affair, it is low theatre with no sincerity, beauty and affectionate bonds. We have seen how Rachel commanded her husband. The woman who came between the two is dead and her husband gone. Women bring more and more calamity. Roger Mason starts drinking he is almost crazy, he does not care if he lives or dies. It is all due to womankind. Goody has brought about the fall of Roger Mason and becomes instrument in the fall of Joceline.

References

1. William Golding, The Inheritors (London : Faber and Faber, 1961), P. 35.
2. William Golding, The Pyramid, (London : Faber and Faber, 1983), P. 16.
3. William Golding, Darkness visible, (London Faber and Faber, 1988), P. 99.

4. William Golding, The Paper Man (London : Faber and Faber, 1988), P. 76
5. William Golding, The spire (London : Faber and Faber, 1965), P. 57.